

EduNetAI: Personalized Learning AI-Powered Education Platform

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Abstract— To build a dynamic and personalized learning environment, this study focuses on the revolutionary potential of AI-driven customization in education. The platform provides personalized learning experiences based on individual preferences and learning styles by integrating artificial intelligence with the MERN stack technology. Through the replacement of conventional one-size-fits-all methods, it develops customized learning paths that take into account the strengths and limits of each learner. The study emphasizes how AI may help advance learning and encourage the use of personalized learning environments. By utilizing the MERN stack, the platform is put at the forefront of educational innovation and offers a seamless and user-friendly experience.

Keywords— Personalized learning, User preferences, AI-driven customization, MERN stack technology, individualized learning routes, learning preferences.

I. INTRODUCTION

The integration of AI in education has steered in a new period of personalized literacy gests for scholars. AI-driven personalization in adaptive literacy platforms tailors educational content and gests to individual learners' unique requirements, preferences, and learning styles. This personalized approach holds the implicit to transfigure traditional education models and ameliorate learners' academic performance, engagement, and overall satisfaction. [1]

In the last many times, e-learning has grown to become an important approach to education that offers inflexibility, scalability, and substantiated learning gests. Adaptive literacy in the environment of learning refers to the intelligent and dynamic customization of literacy content, coffers, and conditioning to meet the unique preferences and requirements of individual learners. By assaying and interpreting learner data, adaptive literacy systems can make informed opinions to give individualized literacy gests, optimize literacy issues, and enhance pupil engagement. [2]

This paper is motivated by the immense implicit held by a substantiated learning system in addressing the challenges of delivering effective online education. It focuses on proposing an effective armature for a substantiated learning system. It elaborates on colorful ways and challenges for such a system and proposes results to encounter these challenges. [3]

II. PROBLEM FORMULATION

The conventional education system's one-size-fits-all approach frequently falls short of meeting each student's unique needs, preferences, and learning preferences. A lack of personalization can result in worse academic progress, disengagement, and general learning experience dissatisfaction. Moreover, scaling, efficiency,

and effectiveness in satisfying the changing needs of learners are hindered by the manual generation and delivery of instructional content. [5]

Our project's problem formulation centers on creating a dynamic and personalized learning platform that uses artificial intelligence (AI) to tailor educational content to each student's unique learning preferences, styles, and performance indicators in order to address these issues. The goal is to provide each student with individualized learning routes and materials in real-time by utilizing machine learning algorithms that are embedded into the platform. In addition, the project aims to leverage the technology of the MERN (MongoDB, Express.js, React.js, Node.js) stack to offer a strong basis for the platform's development, guaranteeing scalability, flexibility, and effectiveness in providing customized learning experiences. [6]

Overall, the problem formulation of our project involves creating an innovative solution to the lack of personalization in traditional education systems by harnessing the power of AI and modern technology to revolutionize the learning experience for students worldwide.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Personalized Learning Platforms:

The body of investigation on the subject emphasizes how significant individualized learning stages are for the assembly of the different necessities and inclinations of personal understudies. Personalized learning frameworks boost understudy engagement, scholastic achievement, and common learning involvement fulfillment, concurring with studies.

B. Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Education:

Researchers are looking at how AI might progress instruction and learning forms, and this has drawn a parcel of consideration to the utilization of AI in instruction [7]. By assessing each learner's interesting learning inclinations, styles, and execution measures, AI-driven personalization has been illustrated to improve learner results [8].

C. MERN Stack Technology in Education:

The MERN stack technology's effectiveness, adaptability, and flexibility have made it a prevalent choice for making instructive stages. Investigate has demonstrated that the MERN stack is productive in giving custom fitted learning openings and speeding up the conveyance of guidelines materials [9].

D. Importance of User-Centric Design:

The user-centric plan plays an urgent part in the advancement of our energetic and personalized learning stage. By setting the needs, inclinations, and encounters of clients at the cutting edge of the plan preparation, we guarantee that the stage is natural, locked in, and successful in assembly the assorted needs of learners.

E. Data Security and Privacy:

With the expanding digitization of travel administrations, concerns almost information security and protection have picked up conspicuousness. Learning stages must actualize strong security measures to protect users' individual and monetary data from cyber dangers and unauthorized access.

IV. METHODOLOGY

Our energetic and personalized learning stage was created utilizing a handle that incorporates numerous vital components planning to ensure the viable utilize of AI-driven customization and the utilization of the MERN (MongoDB, Express.js, React.js, Node.js) stack technology.

Figure 1. Architectural Diagram

A. Data Collection:

Apart from these methods, observational methods were also utilized for information collecting, wherein client intuitive with the stage were archived and inspected. To give a total picture of client requests, overviews were utilized to collect information on inclinations and client fulfillment. In expansion, center gather talks were held to assist with specific subjects or issues that were found all through the information gathering method. Generally, wealthy and shifted information was delivered by combining quantitative and subjective techniques, permitting for in-depth investigation and interpretation.

Data Source	Quantitative Methods	Qualitative Methods
User Interactions	Number of clicks, time spent on pages, frequency of visits	User feedback surveys, interviews
User Preferences	Ratings, scores, preferences	Open-ended questions, focus group
Performance Metrics	Quiz scores, completion rates, progress indicators	User testimonials, case studies
Demographic Data	Age, gender, location	User profiles, demographic surveys

Table 1. Data Collection

B. Research Design:

This ponder will utilize a mixed-method inquire about plan, combining both quantitative and subjective approaches. The mixed-method plan permits for a comprehensive investigation of the affect of AI-driven personalization on learners' execution, giving profitable experiences into the viability and encounters of personalized learning.

C. Data Analysis:

Quantitative investigation envelops expressive insights, which give an outline of learners' execution and engagement levels based on quantitative information collected from client intuitive, inclinations, and execution measurements. [10] Also, comparative investigation will be conducted to compare execution results between diverse bunches of clients, such as those who have experienced personalized learning versus those who have not. This investigation points to distinguish any noteworthy contrasts in scholarly accomplishment, engagement, and fulfillment.

Qualitative examination includes topical examination, which distinguishes common topics and designs in subjective information gotten from client criticism studies, interviews, or center groups.[11] This investigation gives subjective experiences into learners' encounters, recognitions, and states of mind toward personalized learning on our platform.

D. Implications and Recommendations:

Key proposals incorporate refining personalized learning calculations, improving client interface plans for way better ease of use, and persistently assessing stage adequacy [12]. This approach emphasizes the significance of user-centric plans and progressing advancement in instructive technology.

Overall, our extension proposes promising suggestions for teachers and engineers, advertising experiences into how personalized learning stages can improve learner results and adjust to advancing instructive needs.

V. RESULT DISCUSSION

The Comes About Dialog segment presents an investigation of the discoveries, highlighting key bits of knowledge and suggestions for the study's results. It offers a comprehensive elucidation of the comes about and their centrality in tending to the inquiry about objectives.

A. Courses Creation with AI:

Teachers seem utilize AI apparatuses to create course substance, make lesson plans, plan evaluations, and set up course schedules.

Figure 2. Customized Course Creation

Figure 3. Content Creation for courses

B. Student Enrollment:

Students could browse through available courses, select the ones that interest them, and enroll themselves in these courses.

Figure 4. Interactive Home Page

C. User Feedback Analysis Overview:

AI could assist teachers in grading assignments and providing feedback to students, based on pre-defined criteria or customizable rubrics.

D. AI Chatbot Assistance:

Teachers can utilize AI chatbots to assist in course creation, while students can use them to resolve doubts during their course study.

Figure 5. Interactive Assistance with Chatbot

E. Interactive Quizzes:

Each module of the course will include interactive quizzes to assess student understanding and reinforce learning.

F. Discussion Forums:

Dedicated discussion forums will be available for each course, allowing students to engage in academic discussions and share insights.

G. User Profile Management:

This feature allows users to create and manage their profiles, providing essential information such as demographics, learning goals, and preferences.

Figure 6. User Profile Creation

VI. CONCLUSION

A basic turning point in the change of learning situations and the improvement of understudy comes about is the presentation of AI-driven personalization in the classroom. Our activity illustrates the critical affect of utilizing AI advances to customize instruction and make comprehensive, beneficial, and locks in learning situations. We can completely utilize AI-driven individualized learning in instruction by settling moral issues and making ventures in educator preparation.

Our AI-enabled learning stage energizes learners to effectively lock in with substance by advertising real-time input, versatile substance conveyance, and custom-made learning courses. This empowers more profound comprehension and higher levels of competency.

Furthermore, the utilization of AI reduces the requirement for ordinary one-size-fits-all strategies, advancing value and inclusivity in instruction by pleasing a run of learning styles and aptitudes.

Looking ahead, this venture envisions a future of our ponder including the extending corpus of information on AI-driven personalization in instruction by emphasizing how it might progress understudy results and alter the nature of learning. Our objective is to engage understudies and progress instruction for the advantage of society by utilizing AI advances to construct versatile, learner-centric learning situations.

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